

The rice crop received 861.9 mm total rainfall in 1985-86 and 1,050.1 mm in 1987-88; lentil received 51.8 mm in 1985-86 and 74.1 mm in 1987-88.

Application of butachlor in wet season and prometryn in dry season, with and without paraquat, reduced weed dry weight in rice the most (Table 1). In lentil, interculture with intrarow hand weeding reduced weed dry weight the most.

Highest rice grain and straw yields were with interculture twice plus intrarow hand weeding, followed by hand weeding and chemical control. Highest lentil yield was with preemergence application of butachlor in wet season and prometryn in dry season. Interculture was least effective in both crops.

Table 2. Economics^a of weed control treatments in rice - lentil sequence at BHU, Varanasi, India, 1985-88.

Treatment	Mean yield (t/ha)				Value of produce (\$/ha)	Total cost of land preparation and weed control (\$/ha)	Return to land preparation and weed control (\$/ha)	Benefit to-cost ratio
	Rice		Lentil					
	Grain	Straw	Grain	Straw				
T1	0.4	3.0	0.8	1.3	406.35	250.00	156.35	0.63
T2	2.6	4.4	1.2	1.7	831.07	367.65	463.42	1.26
T3	1.3	3.7	0.9	1.3	551.72	279.41	272.31	0.97
T4	3.2	4.8	1.2	1.4	927.93	308.82	619.11	2.01
T5	2.9	4.1	0.8	1.1	749.00	280.88	468.12	1.67
T6	3.0	4.2	1.3	1.6	926.41	295.66	630.75	2.13
T7	2.9	4.2	1.3	2.3	940.29	306.29	634.00	2.07

^aPrice of produce: Rice: grain - \$132.35/t, straw - \$14.71/t; lentil: grain - 330.88/t, straw - 21.74/t. Cost of treatments: Land Preparation (1) \$8.82/ha, hand weeding (1) \$29.41/ha, interculture by dryland weeder (1) \$7.35/ha, intrarow hand weeding (1) \$7.35/ha, spraying of herbicide (1) \$4.41/ha, butachlor at \$13.23/kg ai, prometryn at \$13.78/kg ai, and paraquat at \$23.85/kg ai. General cost of cultivation: \$214.72/ha.

On a pooled mean basis, highest net return was with preemergence application of butachlor in rice and prometryn following paraquat in lentil (Table 2). □

Managing other pests

Effect of bund dimensions on rodent infestation in irrigated ricefields

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We surveyed 83 transplanted irrigated ricefields 1987-88 to examine the relationship between rodent infestation and the width and height of bunds. Rodent infestation was measured as the

Correlation between rodent infestation and bund dimensions.^a Hyderabad, India.

Bund variable	Crop stage ^b (r value)				
	Seedling (13)	Tillering (19)	Booting (17)	Flowering (21)	Maturity (13)
Width (W)	0.87**	0.79**	0.82**	0.44*	0.77**
Height (H)	0.83**	0.57	0.78**	0.78**	0.63**
W × H	0.80**	0.63**	0.78**	0.64**	0.61**

^aSignificance at the 5% (*) and 1% (**) levels. ^bNumbers in parentheses indicate sample size.

number of live burrows/ 10 m.

The correlation between rodent infestation and bund width was significant at all stages of the crop growth; that between infestation and

bund height was significant at all stages except tillering (see table) when rodents establish themselves. Bund volume (height × width) and infestation were directly related. □

Farming systems

Rice-based cropping sequences for rainfed conditions in midhills of Uttar Pradesh

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Spring rice (Mar-Sep) is the predominant upland crop in the midhills

of Uttar Pradesh. Because currently available spring rice varieties have long duration, cropping cereals and legumes in rotation is not feasible. The most popular 2-yr cropping sequence is upland rice (Mar-Sep) - wheat (Oct-May) - finger millet (Jun-Oct) - fallow (Nov-Mar), for a 150% cropping intensity.

After shortduration (110 d Jun-Oct) upland rice variety VL Dhan 163 was released, we evaluated 5 intensive cropping sequences for production and return 1985-86 at the Hawalbagh

experiment farm (1,250 m, 29 °36'N, 79° 40'). The split-plot design had crop sequence as the main plot and organic and inorganic fertilization as subplots, with four replications. Soil was a sandy loam with medium fertility.

Rainfed short-duration rice was direct seeded in the wet season, followed by wheat variety VL 421, barley VLB 1, pea VL Matar 1, lentil VL Masur 1, and rapeseed T9 in the dry season. Rice was sown the first week of Jun, the winter crops were planted the third week of Oct. Organic fertilizer treatment was

Grain yield and net return of rice-based cropping systems under rainfed upland conditions.^a Almora, India, 1985-86.

Crop sequence	Yield (t/ha)				Total cost (\$/ha)		Net return (\$/ha)		Benefit-cost		Protein (t/ha)		Carbohydrate (t/ha)	
	Rainy season		Dry season		OF	IOF	OF	IOF	OF	IOF	OF	IOF	OF	IOF
	OF	IOF	OF	IOF										
Rice - wheat	2.1	2.4	2.5	2.8	377.4	368.4	205.2	290.2	1.5	1.8	0.46	0.50	3.39	3.83
Rice - barley	2.2	2.4	2.2	2.4	373.3	357.8	152.3	215.4	1.4	1.6	0.42	0.46	3.22	3.51
Rice - pea	2.4	2.7	1.9	2.0	337.8	341.8	615.4	682.4	2.8	3.0	0.55	0.59	2.92	3.22
Rice - lentil	2.5	2.7	1.7	1.8	329.5	324.6	527.5	589.1	2.6	2.8	0.60	0.64	2.90	3.10
Rice - rapeseed	2.3	2.5	0.8	1.0	341.6	340.0	207.5	301.7	1.6	1.9	0.33	0.39	1.94	2.16

^a OF = organic fertilizer, IOF = inorganic fertilizer.

12 t farmyard manure (FYM)/ ha. Inorganic fertilizer treatment was recommended NPK for each rainfed crop. Rice received 60-18-25 kg NPK/ ha. All dry season crops grew successfully

(see table). Highest average net return was from rice - pea, followed by rice - lentil; lowest was from rice - barley. Benefit-cost ratios were highest (above 2.0) for rice - legume and lowest for rice - barley. Yields with FYM averaged

0.21 t/ha lower than with inorganic fertilizers. Net return, benefit-cost ratio, and protein and carbohydrate production were higher with inorganic fertilizers. □

Vegetables for high return and water use efficiency in irrigated rice-based systems

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Opportunities for vegetable cultivation on rice fallows are increasing with new facilities for irrigation in coastal Maharashtra (Konkan). Rainfall is high (2,500-3,500 mm) Jun to Sep with a rain-free post-ribe season. We evaluated rice - rice (Ratna), rice - tomato (Sonali), rice - chili (DPL-C-1), and rice - watermelon (Sugarbaby) for gross return and water use.

Soil is lateritic with 1.65% organic C, 2.3 kg available P/ ha, 242 kg available K/ha, and pH 6.0. Wet season rice was entirely rainfed, planted the first week Jul at 20- × 15cm spacing and harvested the second week Oct. Watermelon was planted at 2 × 1 m the first week of Nov, tomato at 60 × 60 cm and chili at 60 × 45 cm were transplanted the first week of Dec, dry season rice was transplanted the second week of Jan. Dry season irrigation was scheduled at 25 mm crop potential evapotranspiration (CPE) for rice, 30

Gross returns of rice - vegetable cropping systems in coastal Maharashtra, India.

Cropping system	Yield (t/ha)		Gross return (\$)			Increase (%)
	Wet season	Dry season ^a	Wet season	Dry season ^b	Total	
Rice - rice	3.7	4.5 (150.0) ^a	711.5	865.3 (5.8)	1576.8	-
Rice - tomato	3.7	49.0 (75.0)	711.5	3769.2 (50.3)	4480.7	184
Rice - chili	3.7	10.0 (115.0)	711.5	3846.2 (33.4)	4557.7	189
Rice - watermelon	3.7	30.0 (30.0)	711.5	2307.7 (76.9)	3019.2	91

^a Figures in parentheses = water use (cm). ^b Figures in parentheses = gross return (\$)/cm water.

for tomato, 36 for chili, and 10 for watermelon. Depth of irrigation per turn was 50 mm for rice, tomato, and chili, and 20 liters/basin for watermelon. Rice received 100-50-50 kg NPK/ha in both seasons; tomato, 150-75-50; chili, 150-50-50; and watermelon, 100-50-50. Protection from pests was need-based.

Increase in gross income was 184% for rice - tomato, 189% for rice - chili, and 91% for rice - watermelon (see table). Gross returns/cm water used was 8 times higher for rice - tomato, 6 times higher for rice - chili, and 13 times higher for rice - watermelon than for rice - rice. □

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